

International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji

also known as “Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji”

By Edward A S Ross, University of Reading

Entry tags: Mahayana Buddhism, Temple, Religious Group, Rinzai Zen (rinzai shū 臨濟宗), Zen Buddhism, Monastery, Buddhist Traditions, Monasticism, Religious Place, Zen Buddhism, Japanese Buddhist Traditions

International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji (DBZ) is a Rinzai Zen Buddhist Training Monastery located on Beecher Lake in the Catskill Mountains, New York, USA. The monastery is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc. (ZSS), an organization originally established in 1956 by Cornelius Crane (d. 1962) to support the translation work of Daisetsu Teitaro Suzuki (1870–1966). However, the monastery and ZSS’s zen centre, New York Zendo Shobo-ji, were built and created by the second iteration of ZSS, which was led by the work of Eido Tai Shimano Roshi (1932–2018) from 1965 to 2010. When the monastery land was first purchased in 1971, teachers and students connected to ZSS gathered in the autumn for their first five-day sesshin (meditation retreat) on the property. This included Eido Roshi’s teacher, Soen Nakagawa Roshi (1907–1984), who was made abbot of DBZ and Shobo-ji that year. Meditation retreats and residencies would take place in Beecher House, also called Joraku-an, during their early stays on the property, as the monastery was still under construction. Beecher House is situated alongside Beecher Lake, and it was previously owned by Henry Ward Beecher, the brother of Harriet Beecher Stowe, the abolitionist and author of ‘Uncle Tom’s Cabin’. During the initial retreats on the property, a zendo and dharma hall were constructed in the building, and a mural depicting the events of the ‘Flower Sermon’ was painted on a ground floor wall by Soen Roshi’s friend Father Maxima. William Johnstone (1899–1983) was named the chairman of the building committee for the monastery in 1971, and Davis Hamerstrom was selected as the architect. After a visit to Japan with Eido Roshi, Hamerstrom selected Tofuku-ji in Kyoto as the model for the future DBZ. Construction on the monastery was completed in 1975, and the building was dedicated for zen practice on August 9th, 1975. During this time, Soen Roshi, Nyogen Senzaki (1876–1958), Chester Carlson (1906–1968), Jimmy Tanahashi, Haku’un Yasutani Roshi (1885–1973), D. T. Suzuki, and William Johnstone were identified as the founders of DBZ. The building was officially opened on July 4th, 1976 with many of these founders present, and the monastery has been used for residential zen training ever since. Eido Roshi continued as abbot of ZSS and DBZ for 37 years, but this period perpetuated an endemic culture of secrecy surrounding his sexual misconduct with his students. In 2010, the Board of ZSS asked Eido Roshi to step down as abbot, and on December 8th, 2010 he retired in response to the board’s request. Shinge Roko Sherry Chayat Roshi (b. 1943), one of Eido Roshi’s dharma heirs, was installed as abbot of ZSS and DBZ on January 1st, 2011. She led the sangha with compassion and wisdom, teaching her numerous students through zazen and koan practice, until her retirement on October 1st, 2023. Although Shinge Roshi continues to be an active teacher at DBZ, she has passed the abbotship on to one of her dharma heirs, Chigan Roland Jaeckel Roshi (b. 1962). DBZ continues to be an active place for zen practice and retreat. Visitors and students of Zen Buddhism can come to the monastery for Intro to Zen weekends, 7-day sesshins, 3-month kessei (residential stays), and summer internships. The Open Space Program at the Beecher House also welcomes a wide variety of retreats who want to experience the peace of Dai Bosatsu Mountain in America. With support from visitors and external donors, Beecher House was renovated in 2021, and the main monastery building will be renovated following a funding campaign in 2023-2024.

Date Range: 1976 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Beecher Lake, New York

Region tags: North America, United States of America, United States, New York

Beecher Lake is the highest-elevated lake in the Catskill Mountains, New York, USA.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary*. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

– Source 2: Nakagawa, Soen, Nyogen Senzaki, and Eido Shimano. *Namu Dai Bosa: A Transmission of Zen Buddhism to America*. New York: Theatre Arts Books, 1976.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://zenstudies.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Zen Studies Society Website: Listings of ZSS activities, locations, and publications.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.shimanoarchive.com/>

– Source 2 Description: The Shimano Archive: A database of all letters and related media about Eido Tai Shimano Roshi's activities with the Zen Studies Society.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is located in the Catskill Mountains in New York alongside Beecher Lake, the highest elevation lake in the Catskill Mountain Reserve.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzai Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

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Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Type of feature

– Clearing

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

– Plantings

Notes: A section of the grounds are dedicated as a garden to grow food to use in the monastery kitchen.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

– Trackway or road-surface

Notes: A walking path around Beecher Lake for walking meditation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is located in the Catskill Mountain Nature Reserve, New York, which is a largely rural area. It is associated with New York Zendo Shobo-ji, which is located

in the urban setting of Manhattan, New York.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is located in the Catskill Mountain Nature Reserve, New York, which is a largely rural area. The closest town to the monastery is Livingston Manor, New York. The monastery is accessible by car along rural roads. Buses do travel to Livingston Manor, but another mode of transport is needed to reach the monastery grounds.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

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Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

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Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

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Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

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Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. The land was initially owned by Henry Ward Beecher, the brother of Harriet Beecher Stowe, and Beecher House was initially constructed during his time. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, Beecher House was renovated, was given the name Joraku-an, and has been used for zen training activities. Beecher House was renovated and restored in 2021.

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A single structure

– Yes

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Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: No

One single feature

–Other [specify]: No

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↳ A group of structures:

– No

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↳ A group of features:

– No

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↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

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↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

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↳ Worship:

– Communal

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↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. The land was initially owned by Henry Ward Beecher, the brother of Harriet Beecher Stowe, and Beecher House was initially constructed during his time. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, Beecher House was renovated, was given the name Joraku-an, and has been used for zen training activities. Beecher House was renovated and restored in 2021.

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↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. The land was initially owned by Henry Ward Beecher, the brother of Harriet Beecher Stowe, and Beecher House was initially constructed during his time. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, Beecher House was renovated, was given the name Joraku-an, and has been used for zen training activities. Beecher House was renovated and restored in 2021.

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Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

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Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

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– Yes

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↳ A single structure

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↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: The temple is modelled after Tofuku-ji in Kyoto, Japan.

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↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: No

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↳ A group of structures:

– No

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Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

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↳ Worship:

– Communal

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↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

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– Yes

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– Yes

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↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

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↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, the main temple structure, which was modelled after after Tofuku-ji in Kyoto, Japan. It includes a gravel zen garden. The building was completed in 1975, it was first dedicated on August 18, 1975, and was officially opened on July 4, 1976. As of 2023, the Zen Studies Society is raising funds to renovate the main temple building.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: It is a small wood cottage.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ A group of features:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Worship:

– Individual

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– I don't know

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included O-an, a small wood cottage. It sleeps 2 people and is frequently used by monastery practitioners for short stays.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ A single structure

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: The gatehouse was designed as a sanmon.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ A group of features:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha. This included a sanmon, the gatehouse complex, at the roadside entrance to monastery grounds. The gatehouse was constructed to commemorate Eido Tai Shimano's 50th anniversary of coming to the United States and was dedicated on August 12, 2012.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras.* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen training monastery that is not dedicated to a particular deity or non-human being. However, chanting towards Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, the bodhisattva of compassion, occurs on a daily basis.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: There are two major places for honoring ancestors at International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: the monastery Dharma Hall and the Sangha Meadow. The Dharma Hall in the monastery has an altar adorned with images and name plates for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society Sangha. The Sangha Meadow is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried there.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Notes: The monastery itself is not a cenotaph, but it does have cenotaphs on its grounds. There are two major places for honoring ancestors at International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: the monastery Dharma Hall and the Sangha Meadow. The Dharma Hall in the monastery has an altar adorned with images and name plates for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society Sangha. The Sangha Meadow is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried there.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: There are two major places for honoring ancestors at International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: the monastery Dharma Hall and the Sangha Meadow. The Dharma Hall in the monastery has an altar adorned with images and name plates for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society Sangha. The Sangha Meadow is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried there.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji was purchased, constructed, and is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York.

Reference: Nakagawa, Soen, Nyogen Senzaki, and Eido Shimano. *Namu Dai Bosa: A Transmission of Zen Buddhism to America*. New York: Theatre Arts Books, 1976.

Specify

– Other [specify]: Zen Studies Society Inc.

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji was purchased, constructed, and is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New

York.

Reference: Nakagawa, Soen, Nyogen Senzaki, and Eido Shimano. *Namu Dai Bosa: A Transmission of Zen Buddhism to America*. New York: Theatre Arts Books, 1976.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: The monastery complex was commissioned by the Zen Studies Society and was constructed by devotees and external contracting companies.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: Although not specifically divine intervention, Soen Nakagawa identified the land of Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji with the mountain he initially trained on as a student in Japan, Dai Bosatsu Mountain in Yamanashi Prefecture. To him, the mountain in the Catskills was a revival of the original Dai Bosatsu Mountain.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: The purchase of the land and construction of the monastery complex was funded by donations through the Zen Studies Society Inc.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Malone, Kobutsu Kevin Christopher. "The Shimano Archive - Eido Roku", 2016. <https://www.shimanoarchive.com/>.

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The purchase of the land and construction of the monastery complex was funded by donations through the Zen Studies Society Inc.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Malone, Kobutsu Kevin Christopher. "The Shimano Archive - Eido Roku", 2016. <https://www.shimanoarchive.com/>.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: A country retreat center for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Malone, Kobutsu Kevin Christopher. "The Shimano Archive - Eido Roku", 2016. <https://www.shimanoarchive.com/>.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex consists of several buildings and clearings. The land was initially owned by Henry Ward Beecher, the brother of Harriet Beecher Stowe, and Beecher House was initially constructed during his time. Following the purchase of the land by the Zen Studies Society, Beecher House was renovated, was given the name Joraku-an, and has been used for zen training activities. Several buildings and clearings were constructed to accommodate the sangha during this time. This included Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, the main temple structure, O-an, a small wood cottage, and the sanmon, the entry gatehouse complex.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Tanahashi, Kazuaki, and Roko Sherry Chayat, eds.. Endless Vow: The Zen Path of Soen Nakagawa. Edited by Kazuaki Tanahashi and Roko Sherry Chayat. London: Shambhala Publications Ltd., 1996.

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery complex is associated with the mountain on which it is constructed. This is because Soen Nakagawa, the Founding Abbot, saw it as a re-emergence of the mountain which he initially trained on as a young monk, Dai Bosatsu Mountain in Yamanashi Prefecture, Japan.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Tanahashi, Kazuaki, and Roko Sherry Chayat, eds.. Endless Vow: The Zen Path of Soen Nakagawa. Edited by Kazuaki Tanahashi and Roko Sherry Chayat. London: Shambhala Publications Ltd., 1996.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: A zen garden is attached to the main monastery building.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main monastery building is the primary place for meditation practice and teaching in the complex, and the other buildings, Beecher House and O-an, are generally only used when it is not possible to solely use the main monastery building.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

|

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Unclear

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The structure was designed after Tofuku-ji in Kyoto, Japan, and the materials used were meant to be as authentic as possible while adapting for New York weather. This included many man-made features and appliances.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: There are a wide variety of decorations across the grounds of Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji grounds. This includes murals, paintings, statuary, carvings, and reliefs. Most of the art depicts events or figures from Rinzaï Zen Buddhist history, people from the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, representations of the Buddhist Dharma, and memorial dedications.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: There are several permanent decorations on the monastery grounds and in the buildings. A gravel zen garden is attached to the outside of the main monastery building. There are also several statues and carvings placed around monastery grounds and in the Sangha Meadow. Murals are painted and drawn inside Beecher House and the main monastery building.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The main monastery building is designed after Tofuku-ji in Kyoto, Japan and features design elements from traditional Japanese Buddhist temples. There is a permanent zen garden attached to the south-eastern wall of the main monastery building. There are also several statues and carvings placed around monastery grounds and in the Sangha Meadow.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There are several murals painted on walls in Beecher House, including the mural of the Flower Sermon, and the main monastery building, including a drawing of Avalokiteśvara in the Dharma Hall.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There are several paintings, reliefs, bells, chains, woodblocks, and signs attached to the various buildings which are hung but can be removed. Most of these are for specific uses or to represent different aspects of Rinzai Zen Buddhism.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: There are many figures depicted in the art around monastery grounds. Many carvings, paintings, and statues depict bodhisattvas and buddhas. There are also plenty of paintings and calligraphy depicting figures from Rinzai Zen Buddhist history and the history of the Zen Studies Society. Some animals are also depicted as part of calligraphy.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzai Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are several images of bodhisattvas and buddhas throughout the monastery grounds and buildings. Most images depict Shakyamuni Buddha, Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon, and Jizo Bodhisattva.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are several calligraphy, paintings, and photos of humans in the monastery buildings. This includes people from Rinzaï Zen Buddhist history, like Bodhidharma and the original devotees of Shakyamuni Buddha, and the history of the Zen Studies Society, including Soen Nakagawa and Eido Tai Shimano.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are some images of animals present within calligraphy and murals as part of Rinzaï Zen Buddhist narratives. This includes a calligraphy of an ox, referencing the Ten Ox-Herding Pictures.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzaï Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji houses countless works of calligraphy and art from masters in the dharma lineage of the sangha. Most of the calligraphy is stored in a private area and is not accessible to the public, but what is displayed depicts references to Buddhist history and representations of the Dharma.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzaï Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There are several calligraphy depicting ensō, ink-wash circles representing a variety of aspects of enlightenment. Some of these ensō were painted by Soen Nakagawa.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzai Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: There are quite a few calligraphy and paintings depicting floral motifs in both Beecher House and the main monastery building.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Many of the calligraphy at the monastery depict phrases related to the practices of the masters of the Zen Studies Society's lineage. There are calligraphy painted by Soen Nakagawa, Gempo Yamamoto, Eido Tai Shimano, and Shinge Roko Sherry Chayat housed in the monastery.

Reference: Ross, Edward A S. "Following Traces: The Ten Ox-herding Pictures and Rinzai Zen in North America", *Symposia: The Journal of Religion*, 10 (2019).

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There are many paintings kept in storage which were not available for view.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of paintings, calligraphy, and artwork which are not on public display and in storage. These works are occasionally rotated into display. There is also a statue of Avalokiteśvara in a cabinet in the zendo of the main monastery building. The doors are partially opened during times of active practice, but it is only opened fully for cleaning and special occasions.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of paintings, calligraphy, and artwork which are not on

public display and in storage. These works are occasionally rotated into display. There is also a statue of Avalokiteśvara in a cabinet in the zendo of the main monastery building. The doors are partially opened during times of active practice, but it is only opened fully for cleaning and special occasions.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Are there statues present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many statues present on monastery grounds and in the buildings. There is a large bronze buddha statue on the far side of Beecher Lake which was placed when the land was first purchased by the Zen Studies Society in 1971. On each altar in all of the buildings on the monastery grounds, there is a buddha statue which is used for daily practice.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: There are many statues present on monastery grounds and in the buildings. On each altar in all of the buildings on the monastery grounds, there is a buddha statue which is used for daily practice.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are many statues present on monastery grounds and in the buildings. There is a large bronze buddha statue on the far side of Beecher Lake which was placed when the land was first purchased by the Zen Studies Society in 1971. On each altar in all of the buildings on the monastery grounds, there is a buddha statue which is used for daily practice.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Statues of humans:

– No

Notes: There are many statues present on monastery grounds and in the buildings. There is a large bronze buddha statue on the far side of Beecher Lake which was placed when the land was first purchased by the Zen Studies Society in 1971. On each altar in all of the buildings on the monastery grounds, there is a buddha statue which is used for daily practice.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..

Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are artworks preserved in storage which are not available for public view.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of reliefs and carvings around monastery grounds, but most are around the Sangha Meadow. There are some depictions of buddhas and bodhisattvas on steles and stones in the Sangha Meadow. This includes a depiction of Jizo Bodhisattva alongside a quote from Basho.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of reliefs and carvings around monastery grounds, but most are around the Sangha Meadow. There are some depictions of buddhas and bodhisattvas on steles and stones in the Sangha Meadow. This includes a depiction of Jizo Bodhisattva alongside a quote from Basho.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

Notes: There are a variety of reliefs and carvings around monastery grounds, but most are around the Sangha Meadow. There are some depictions of buddhas and bodhisattvas on steles and stones in the Sangha Meadow. This includes a depiction of Jizo Bodhisattva alongside a quote from Basho.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of reliefs and carvings around monastery grounds, but most are around the Sangha Meadow. There are some depictions of buddhas and bodhisattvas on steles and stones in the Sangha Meadow. This includes a depiction of Jizo Bodhisattva alongside a quote from Basho.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are artworks preserved in storage which are not available for public view.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of paintings around Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji. There are wall murals in Beecher House and the main monastery building depicting the Flower Sermon and the Ten-Thousand-Armed Avalokiteśvara respectively. There are also a variety of paintings hung on the walls of all buildings. These include paintings of Soen Nakagawa meditating in Beecher House and Bodhidharma in the meeting room of the main monastery building.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: The mural in Beecher House is located in the room below the Dharma Hall and is painted on a wall facing Beecher Lake. The mural depicts the events of the Flower Sermon, where Mahakasyapa receives heart-mind to heart-mind transmission from Shakyamuni Buddha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: The mural is painted onto prepared plaster wall.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: There are several paintings of buddhas and bodhisattvas in monastery buildings. These include Avalokiteśvara/Guanyin/Kannon and Jizo Bodhisattva.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The mural in Beecher House is located in the room below the Dharma Hall and is painted on a wall facing Beecher Lake. The mural depicts the events of the Flower Sermon, where Mahakasyapa receives heart-mind to heart-mind transmission from Shakyamuni Buddha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The mural in Beecher House is located in the room below the Dharma Hall and is painted on a wall facing Beecher Lake. The mural depicts the events of the Flower Sermon, where Mahakasyapa receives heart-mind to heart-mind transmission from Shakyamuni Buddha. There are also paintings depicting events from Zen Studies Society history, including a painting of Soen Nakagawa meditating in the zendo of Beecher House while the main monastery building was under construction.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There are artworks preserved in storage which are not available for public view.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: There are several carvings and inscriptions on the monastery grounds. Most of these inscriptions are calligraphy carved into wood or stone. They are found in and on the buildings and in the Sangha Meadow. These inscriptions usually are used for signage, depict the Buddhist Dharma, or dedication for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society sangha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: There are several carvings and inscriptions on the monastery grounds. Most of these inscriptions are calligraphy carved into wood or stone. They are found in and on the buildings and in the Sangha Meadow. These inscriptions usually are used for signage, depict the Buddhist Dharma, or dedication for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society sangha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...

– Yes

Notes: There are several carvings and inscriptions on the monastery grounds. Most of these inscriptions are calligraphy carved into wood or stone. They are found in and on the buildings and in the Sangha Meadow. These inscriptions usually are used for signage, depict the Buddhist Dharma, or dedication for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society sangha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: There are several carvings and inscriptions on the monastery grounds. Most of these inscriptions are calligraphy carved into wood or stone. They are found in and on the buildings and in the Sangha Meadow. These inscriptions usually are used for signage, depict the Buddhist Dharma, or dedication for deceased members of the Zen Studies Society sangha.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There are artworks preserved in storage which are not available for public view.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Notes: There are artworks preserved in storage which are not available for public view.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery features several works of art across its grounds. This includes murals of bodhisattvas and stories from Buddhist history, calligraphy depicting Buddhist concepts, and statues depicting Buddhist deities.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There are several statues, carvings, and paintings of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas across the monastery grounds. This includes a mural depicting the events of the Flower Sermon in Beecher House, a carving of Jizo Bodhisattva near the Sangha Meadow, statues of Shakyamuni Buddha and Avalokiteśvara in the monastery, and a bronze Buddha statue also sits on the shore of Beecher Lake across from Beecher House.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Notes: There are some mural images of tantric forms of bodhisattvas in the monastery. In particular, a drawing of the Ten-Thousand Armed Avalokiteśvara adorns the north-western wall of the Dharma Hall.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Most of the images, calligraphy, and murals are meant to demonstrate aspects of the Buddhist Dharma and promote practice towards enlightenment.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: There are several calligraphy paintings depicting human practitioners from Zen Buddhist history, including an image of Bodhidharma in the monastery dining hall and a painting of Soen Nakagawa in the monastery Dharma Hall.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: There are some mural images of bodhisattvas in the monastery engaging in supernatural activity. In particular, a drawing of the Ten-Thousand Armed Avalokiteśvara adorns the north-western wall of the Dharma Hall, and a carving of Jizo Bodhisattva riding a cloud is located near the Sangha Meadow.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Some murals depict human stories from Buddhist history, including a painting of the events of the Flower Sermon below the Dharma Hall in Beecher House.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary..* Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: There is no worship of the dead, but rather veneration of deceased masters. There is also a daily ritual by members of the monastery to chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: Sangha members are buried on the grounds in the Sangha Meadow, but corpses are not treated on the monastery grounds.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: The funerary traditions in the Sangha Meadow are recent and have no clear grave goods around the stones. Due to the private nature of funerals, it is unethical to speculate on the presence or absence of such features, as this knowledge is the sole right of the survivors.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Notes: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The "Sangha Meadow" is located along the road to Beecher Lake. This clearing is a cemetery for sangha members of this tradition. A portion of Eido Shimano Roshi and Soen Nakagawa Roshi's remains are buried here.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: There is a daily ritual by members of the monastery to chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: There is a daily ritual by members of the monastery to chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras*. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: There is a daily ritual by members of the monastery to chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras*. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are statues of buddhas and bodhisattvas present on each altar used on the monastery grounds. There are also several statues of buddhas and bodhisattvas around monastery grounds. Although most are visible, there is a statue of Avalokiteśvara in a cabinet in the zendo of the main monastery building. The doors are partially opened during times of active practice, but it is only opened fully for cleaning and special occasions.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary*.. Edited by Shinge

Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: There are statues of buddhas and bodhisattvas present on each altar used on the monastery grounds. There are also several statues of buddhas and bodhisattvas around monastery grounds. Most of these statues are clearly visible.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: There is a statue of Avalokiteśvara in a cabinet in the zendo of the main monastery building. The doors are partially opened during times of active practice, but it is only opened fully for cleaning and special occasions.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji: 40th Anniversary.. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, 2016.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Notes: Rather than supernatural monitoring, the tradition focuses on karmic seeds which actions, speech, and thought produce.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Part of daily practice at the monastery involves chanting to the various buddhas, bodhisattvas, and previous masters associated with the Zen Studies Society. This chanting includes passages from the Heart Sutra, Lotus Sutra, and the Zen Studies Society's dharma lineage.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Part of daily practice at the monastery involves chanting to the various buddhas, bodhisattvas, and previous masters associated with the Zen Studies Society. This chanting

includes passages from the Heart Sutra, Lotus Sutra, and the Zen Studies Society's dharma lineage.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Several ritual activities take place at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, including daily chanting, offering of incense, and honouring ancestors. These occur in small and large-scale depending on the number of visitors and residents present at that time.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Several ritual activities take place at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, including daily chanting, offering of incense, and honouring ancestors. These occur in small and large-scale depending on the number of visitors and residents present at that time.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Several ritual activities take place at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, including daily chanting, offering of incense, and honouring ancestors. These occur in small and large-scale depending on the number of visitors and residents present at that time.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: On populous days, ritual activity can include up to 100 people on festival days, but there tends to be an average of 20-40 for larger standard days.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Most occur daily, but some happen every second day, weekly, or annually. This is largely

associated with different chants and forms of offering activities.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras*. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: There are points where a student can speak to their teacher privately, dokusan. In these meetings, students can have conversations with the teacher to test the student's progress and understanding.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors and residents are expected to follow the rules of the monastery when on its grounds. This includes taking a number of precepts, such as abstaining from intoxicants and sexual activity. It is quite common for monastics and residents to correct residents and visitors when they make form mistakes while practicing or performing rituals in the monastery. These corrections are meant to help the resident or visitor practice more effectively.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Much of the chanting involves all present members chanting in unison. There is also integration of musical instruments and offering practices during the chanting in many cases.

Reference: Chayat, Shinge Sherry, ed.. *The Zen Studies Society Daily Sutras*. Edited by Shinge Sherry Chayat. New York: Zen Studies Society, Inc., 2015.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: When a person visits the monastery for a short trip or long stay, it is traditionally expected that the visitor brings a small offering for the sangha. This is not mandatory, and there are no specific regulations besides food items which can be consumed by vegetarians. There have been cases of valuable objects made as offerings, and these have been maintained in the monastery buildings. Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: When a person visits the monastery for a short trip or long stay, it is traditionally expected that the visitor brings a small offering for the sangha. This is not mandatory, and there are no specific regulations besides food items which can be consumed by vegetarians. There have been cases of valuable objects made as offerings, and these have been maintained in the monastery buildings. Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: When a person visits the monastery for a short trip or long stay, it is traditionally expected that the visitor brings a small offering for the sangha. This is not mandatory, and there are no specific regulations besides food items which can be consumed by vegetarians. There have been cases of valuable objects made as offerings, and these have been maintained in the monastery buildings. Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: When a person visits the monastery for a short trip or long stay, it is traditionally expected that the visitor brings a small offering for the sangha. This is not mandatory, and there are no specific regulations besides food items which can be consumed by vegetarians. There have been cases of valuable objects made as offerings, and these have been maintained in the monastery buildings. Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Notes: When a person visits the monastery for a short trip or long stay, it is traditionally expected that the visitor brings a small offering for the sangha. This is not mandatory, and there are no specific regulations besides food items which can be consumed by vegetarians.

There have been cases of valuable objects made as offerings, and these have been maintained in the monastery buildings. Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Monetary offerings are used to support monastery maintenance and renovation.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Notes: There are many daily tasks required to maintain the monastery, especially since it is frequently accommodates visiting practitioners. This includes waxing the floor daily to prevent mold, cleaning rooms and washing linens, and dusting. Some duties are performed weekly/annually, such as cleaning meditation cushions and dusting altars. These duties are performed by residents of the monastery present at the time of need. There is also a maintenance position for repairs and reconstruction which is assigned by the board of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: There are many daily tasks required to maintain the monastery, especially since it is frequently accommodates visiting practitioners. This includes waxing the floor daily to prevent mold, cleaning rooms and washing linens, and dusting. Some duties are performed weekly/annually, such as cleaning meditation cushions and dusting altars. These duties are performed by residents of the monastery present at the time of need. There is also a maintenance position for repairs and reconstruction which is assigned by the board of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Notes: There are many daily tasks required to maintain the monastery, especially since it is frequently accommodates visiting practitioners. This includes waxing the floor daily to

prevent mold, cleaning rooms and washing linens, and dusting. Some duties are performed weekly/annually, such as cleaning meditation cushions and dusting altars. These duties are performed by residents of the monastery present at the time of need. There is also a maintenance position for repairs and reconstruction which is assigned by the board of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: There are many daily tasks required to maintain the monastery, especially since it is frequently accommodates visiting practitioners. This includes waxing the floor daily to prevent mold, cleaning rooms and washing linens, and dusting. Some duties are performed weekly/annually, such as cleaning meditation cushions and dusting altars. These duties are performed by residents of the monastery present at the time of need. There is also a maintenance position for repairs and reconstruction which is assigned by the board of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: There are many daily tasks required to maintain the monastery, especially since it is frequently accommodates visiting practitioners. This includes waxing the floor daily to prevent mold, cleaning rooms and washing linens, and dusting. Some duties are performed weekly/annually, such as cleaning meditation cushions and dusting altars. These duties are performed by residents of the monastery present at the time of need. There is also a maintenance position for repairs and reconstruction which is assigned by the board of the Zen Studies Society.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen

Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

How strict is pilgrimage:

— optional (common)

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

— Yes

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

— Yes

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Birth
– No

↳ Transition to adulthood
– No

↳ Death
– Yes

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023.
<https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Weddings

Notes: Members of the sangha frequently visit Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji during the year. The monastery was built for the purpose of acting as a country training centre for the sangha of the Zen Studies Society, and many members visit several times per year. There are six sesshins, 7-day meditation retreats, each year, and all members of the sangha are welcome to attend and engage in meditative practice together, provided they pay the fees for food and accommodation. There are also annual festivals to honour the deceased members of the sangha and other bodhisattvas which draw visitors and residents back to the monastery frequently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023.
<https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are frequent community meals at Dai Bosatsu Zendo. These happen twice daily, once after the morning meditation session and once following the midday meditation session. Evening meals are not required on the daily schedule. During sesshin periods, three meals per day are cooked and provided to participants by residents of the monastery at the time. These occur after the morning meditation session, following the midday meditation session, and after the afternoon meditation session. There are also larger community meals during celebrations and festivals, such as

the anniversary celebrations on July 4th or O-Bon festival in August each year.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Notes: There are frequent community meals at Dai Bosatsu Zendo. These happen twice daily, once after the morning meditation session and once following the midday meditation session. Evening meals are not required on the daily schedule. During sesshin periods, three meals per day are cooked and provided to participants by residents of the monastery at the time. These occur after the morning meditation session, following the midday meditation session, and after the afternoon meditation session. There are also larger community meals during celebrations and festivals, such as the anniversary celebrations on July 4th or O-Bon festival in August each year.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

Notes: There are frequent community meals at Dai Bosatsu Zendo. These happen twice daily, once after the morning meditation session and once following the midday meditation session. Evening meals are not required on the daily schedule. During sesshin periods, three meals per day are cooked and provided to participants by residents of the monastery at the time. These occur after the morning meditation session, following the midday meditation session, and after the afternoon meditation session. There are also larger community meals during celebrations and festivals, such as the anniversary celebrations on July 4th or O-Bon festival in August each year.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Meals and sangha dinners usually occur in the dining hall or in the tenzo (kitchen), depending on the number of residents and visitors present at the time.

Notes: There are frequent community meals at Dai Bosatsu Zendo. These happen twice daily, once after the morning meditation session and once following the midday meditation session. Evening meals are not required on the daily schedule. During sesshin periods, three meals per day are cooked and provided to participants by residents of the monastery at the time. These occur after the morning meditation session, following the midday meditation session, and after the afternoon meditation session. There are also larger community meals during celebrations and festivals, such as the anniversary celebrations on July 4th or O-Bon festival in August each year.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur

each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Frequency of festivals

— specify: O-Bon, a festival honouring the deceased, occurs each year in August. An anniversary celebration is held each year on July 4th.

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

— All members

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

— Yes

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Notes: During the O-Bon and Anniversary celebrations, the monastery is decorated and cleaned to accommodate many visitors. The O-Bon festival in particular requires the production of many paper lanterns, which are inscribed with the names of the deceased and floated on Beecher Lake at night.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023.
<https://zenstudies.org/>.

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: During the O-Bon and Anniversary celebrations, the monastery is decorated and cleaned to accommodate many visitors. The O-Bon festival in particular requires the production of many paper lanterns, which are inscribed with the names of the deceased and floated on Beecher Lake at night.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023.
<https://zenstudies.org/>.

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

Notes: The altars in the Dharma halls are specifically cleaned during the O-Bon season to honour the deceased.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023.
<https://zenstudies.org/>.

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: around 100, this is usually restricted by the number of beds available for visitors to remain at the monastery overnight.

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably housed at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have

almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites
- Religious professionals

Notes: Festivals, including O-Bon and the anniversary of the opening of Dai Bosatsu Zendo, occur each year and are celebrated by many members of the Zen Studies Society sangha each year. Members and their families tend to make the trip up to the monastery for these festivals in August and July respectively. On years for special dates, these celebrations have almost 100 attendees, but attendance is usually limited to numbers which can be reasonably houses at the monastery overnight. These celebrations usually have a community, vegetarian meal, meditation, chanting, and performances.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- Yes

Notes: Although there are no specific healing rituals practiced at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, the sangha provides space for many groups to engage in healing practice with their Open Spaces at the Beecher House program. The sangha at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji also offers a daily ritual where residents of the monastery chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Incubation

- No

↳ Healing magic

- No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Space for community healing practices

Notes: Although there are no specific healing rituals practiced at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji, the sangha provides space for many groups to engage in healing practice with their Open Spaces at the Beecher House program. The sangha at Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji also offers a daily ritual where residents of the monastery chant the names of recently deceased people, usually by request from a sangha member, for 49 days after their death to ensure they move to a positive rebirth.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery. The sangha offers training stays from a weekend to three months for lay practitioners throughout the year. Monastics and lay practitioners are not restricted by gender, ethnicity, or class.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery. The sangha offers training stays from a weekend to three months for lay practitioners throughout the year.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery. The sangha offers training stays from a weekend to three months for lay practitioners throughout the year. Monastics and lay practitioners are not restricted by gender, ethnicity, or class.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery. The sangha offers training stays from a weekend to three months for lay practitioners throughout the year. Monastics and practitioners are not restricted by gender, ethnicity, or class.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Notes: Monastic practitioners live at the monastery full-time during their zen training period. There is usually a head monk in charge of daily activity at the monastery. The sangha offers training stays from a weekend to three months for lay practitioners throughout the year. Monastics and practitioners are not restricted by gender, ethnicity, or class.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners within this sangha are stratified according to vows and spiritual attainments. Lay practitioners are expected to follow the ethical guidelines of the Zen Studies Society when on monastery grounds, but they may also take vows in their daily life through jukai. Monastic practitioners take further vows and run the daily activities at the monastery. As monastics continue their practice, they can receive the osho title, indicating successful

completion of their zen training. Monastics are granted the title roshi once they have been recognized as an "enlightened zen master".

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: Certain spaces within the monastery, particularly the archives and abbot's apartments are restricted to approved members of the sangha.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen Buddhist Training Monastery that offers several different training and residency programs for religious specialists. The monastery complex has rooms available in three buildings for stay, including the main temple building, Beecher House, and O-an cottage.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is a Rinzai Zen Buddhist Training Monastery. It offers several different training programs for religious specialists. Lay practitioners can come to the monastery for Intro to Zen weekends, week-long intensive meditative retreats (sesshin), three-month training stays (kessei), and summer internships. Following ordination, monastics stay at the monastery to complete their zen training.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. The cooperation is run by a board of directors, which consists of the abbot of International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji and New York Zendo Shobo-ji as an ex-officio member and 5-11 board officers.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned

with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. The cooperation is run by a board of directors, which consists of the abbot of International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji and New York Zendo Shobo-ji as an ex-officio member and 5-11 board officers. The officers are usually members of the International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji sangha. Although officers will spend time at the monastery during the year, none live at the monastery permanently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. The cooperation is run by a board of directors, which consists of the abbot of International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji and New York Zendo Shobo-ji as an ex-officio member and 5-11 board officers. The officers are usually members of the International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji sangha. Although officers will spend time at the monastery during the year, none live at the monastery permanently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. The cooperation is run by a board of directors, which consists of the abbot of International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji and New York Zendo Shobo-ji as an ex-officio member and 5-11 board officers. The officers are usually members of the International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji sangha. Although officers will spend time at the monastery during the year, none live at the monastery permanently.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. Although the cooperation largely runs on donations, the monastery also generates income by providing space and teaching for a number of Zen training retreats to members of the public. These retreats include use of monastery spaces and tools.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. Although the cooperation largely runs on donations, the monastery also generates income by providing space and teaching for a number of Zen training retreats to members of the public. These retreats include use of monastery spaces and tools.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. Although the cooperation largely runs on donations, the monastery also generates income by providing space and teaching for a number of Zen training retreats to members of the public. These retreats include use of monastery spaces and tools.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji is maintained by the Zen Studies Society, Inc., a non-profit cooperation in New York City, New York. Although the cooperation largely runs on donations, the monastery also generates income by providing space and teaching for a number of Zen training retreats to members of the public. These retreats include use of monastery spaces and tools.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "Zen Studies Society By-laws", 2018.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji's grounds and buildings are usually offered as retreat spaces for community groups. This includes their "Open Spaces at Beecher House" program.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji's grounds and buildings are usually offered as retreat spaces for community groups. This includes their "Open Spaces at Beecher House" program.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: International Dai Bosatsu Zendo Kongo-ji has a library with a wide variety of texts regarding Zen and wider, related topics. The store rooms also hold a collection of calligraphy works drawn by figures related to the monastery.

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: There are no specific scriptures associated with International Dai Bosatsu Kongo-ji, but the Zen Studies Society does publish a number of books associated with masters in its lineage. This includes Nyogen Senzaki, Soen Nakagawa, and Eido Shimano's "Namu Dai Bosa: A Transmission of Zen Buddhism to America."

Reference: Zen Studies Society. "The Zen Studies Society", 2023. <https://zenstudies.org/>.

Bibliography

General References

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